

VARIATION OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCE WITH CONCENTRATION OF AQUEOUS SODIUM OLEATE SOLUTIONS IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF ALCOHOLS AND SALT

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Variation of specific conductance of sodium oleate—water with varying concentrations of alcohols has been studied. The results have been explained on the basis of the structure that alcohol molecules arrange themselves in the palisade layers of oleate molecules.

Electrical conductance of solutions of long chain salts in the presence of methyl and ethyl alcohols has been studied by Ward (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 522), Grieger and Kraus (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 380), Rollston and Egerberger (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 983) and Brown, Grieger and Kraus (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 95). It has been found by Brown and co-workers that the behaviour of *isopropyl* alcohol and *tert.*-butyl alcohol is different from that of methyl and ethyl alcohols. The present work has been undertaken with a view to ascertaining if the variation in the concentration of alcohols changes the structure of 0.4*N*-sodium oleate solution in water.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experimental method is the same as recorded in the previous communication (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 135). Results obtained are shown in Table I. Electrical conductance has been studied in most of the cases at five different concentrations and temperatures but the results have been reported only at two temperatures.

TABLE I
Variation of specific conductance with concentration ($\mu \times 10^2$)
Conc. of Na-oleate in all the solutions = 0.4 *N*.

Temp.	In absence of NaCl.	Concentration of NaCl solution.				
		<i>N</i> /1.	<i>N</i> /20.	<i>N</i> /40.	<i>N</i> /80.	<i>N</i> /160.
10% <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.						
30°	1.500	2.174	1.841	1.678	1.582	—
50°	2.293	3.227	2.783	2.527	2.400	—
20% <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.						
30°	1.300	1.870	1.662	1.470	1.404	1.374
50°	2.004	2.773	2.491	2.290	2.033	2.082
30% <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.						
30°	1.042	1.485	1.372	1.158	1.114	...
50°	1.536	2.293	1.991	1.814	1.733	...

TABLE I. (contd.)

Temp.	In absence of NaCl	N/L.	Concentration of NaCl solution. N/20.	N/40.	N/80.	N/160.
40% <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.						
30°	0.8144	...	0.9845	0.9125	0.8840	0.8531
50°	1.2800	...	1.4930	1.4270	1.3630	1.3400
50% <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.						
30°	0.5984	...	0.6431	0.6391	...	...
50°	0.9418	...	1.0920	1.0050	...	...
10% <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.						
30°	1.3660	2.107	1.723	1.493	1.419	1.388
50°	2.126	3.107	2.680	2.400	2.212	2.167
20% <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.						
30°	1.183	...	1.435	1.353	1.242	1.243
50°	1.908	...	2.293	2.138	2.017	1.990
30% <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.						
30°	0.9460	...	1.1620	1.096	1.040	1.000
50°	1.5860	...	1.9090	1.774	1.692	1.635
40% <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.						
30°	0.7568	...	0.8900	0.8350	0.7371	...
50°	1.2300	...	1.4600	1.3570	...	...
50% <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol.						
30°	0.5688	...	...	...	...	...
50°	0.9140	...	...	...	...	...
10% <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol*.						
30°	1.551	2.202	1.893	1.706	1.640	1.614
45°	2.116	2.977	2.567	2.352	2.244	2.208
20% <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol*.						
30°	1.246	1.724	1.487	1.357	1.328	1.272
45°	1.676	2.342	2.017	1.866	1.811	1.743
30% <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol*.						
30°	0.8866	1.180	1.036	0.9687	0.9347	...
45°	1.2110	1.592	1.410	1.3160	...	...

TABLE I (contd.)

Temp.	In absence of NaCl.	$N/1$	Concentration of $N/20$.	NaCl solution. $N/40$.	$N/80$.	$N/160$.
40% <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol*.						
30°	0.5425	...	0.7278	0.6283	0.5696	...
45°	0.7633	...	0.5173	0.8561	0.7923	...
50% <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol*.						
30°	0.2375	...	...	0.2438	...	...
45°	0.3466	...	...	0.3637	...	...
10% <i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol.						
30°	1.641	...	1.945	1.787	1.720	1.643
45°	2.219	...	2.614	2.407	2.221	2.193
30% <i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol.						
30°	0.8806	...	0.8858	0.8874	0.8883	...
50°	1.3850	...	1.4620	1.4460	1.4310	...
40% <i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol.						
30°	0.7066	...	...	...	...	...
50°	0.8872	...	...	...	...	...
50% <i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol.						
30°	0.2703	...	...	...	...	...
50°	0.4903	...	...	...	...	...

*In the case of *n*-butyl alcohol 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 g. of alcohol were dissolved in 100 c.c. of solution. In some cases addition of NaCl separated the alcohol and water layer.

DISCUSSION

From the results in Table I, specific conductance was plotted against the concentration of sodium chloride for each concentration of alcohol, for example in the case of 10% *n*-propyl alcohol the concentrations of sodium chloride taken up were $N/20$, $N/40$, $N/80$ and $N/160$. The specific conductance was plotted against these concentrations of sodium chloride. In the case of lower concentration of *isopropyl* and *n*-propyl alcohol, the plot of μ - c shows curvature. Probably this is due to the fact that alcohol and water molecules form hydrates and these hydrated molecules are broken up by the addition of sodium chloride and the degree of breaking up of hydrated molecules depends on the concentration of sodium chloride as a result of which the plot of μ - c shows a curvature. It is further observed that above and below $N/40$ sodium chloride concentration the nature of the curve is

different; this is due to the fact that at $N/40$ sodium chloride concentration the hydration is just completely broken up and below this concentration the hydration is not broken up. Similar results have been obtained in the case of viscosity, where it has been observed that at $N/40$ sodium chloride concentration the viscosity is minimum due to the complete breaking up of the hydrated molecules.

It has been further observed that at higher concentrations of alcohol the plot of $\mu-c$ does not show so much of curvature as at lower concentrations. This may be due to the fact that at higher concentrations of alcohol, the alcohol molecules replace the water molecules present in between the two layers of oleate molecules as a result of which hydration decreases.

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